

Next-Generation Robotics for Sustainable and Efficient Thermal Shielding of Buildings

Advanced robotics for optimal building efficiency

The ShieldBot project aims to revolutionise the construction industry by integrating advanced robotics with sustainable practices to tackle critical challenges in renovation and building efficiency through three innovative solutions:

InnerShieldBot

Hybrid manipulator designed for internal construction works, applying similar thermal shielding to walls and ceilings to enhance comfort and efficiency.

InspectionShieldBot

Drone-based inspection solution using advanced sensors to assess building exteriors and detect repair or insulation needs, enhanced with a continuum robot for safe inspection of hard-to-reach areas, supporting sustainable maintenance.

FaçadeShieldBot

Cable-driven parallel robot focusing on installing thermal shielding on building façades, improving insulation and reducing energy consumption.

These robotic systems that emphasise the integration of **human-robot collaboration** are supported by:

DigiShield

A BIM-based digital twin platform with AI reasoning that aggregates and analyses data from on-site operations, enabling real-time decision-making and precise project planning.

EcoShield

Innovative, eco-friendly materials for insulation solutions to further minimise the carbon footprint of construction activities

Our Demo Cases

Interior wall and ceiling construction
in office buildings

Inspection and maintenance of
exterior building façades

Exterior façade insulation of
multi-family dwellings

Our Mission

Increase buildings renovation rates

Reduce energy consumption of buildings

Improve smart readiness

Improve users' comfort, wellbeing and health

Keep housing affordable

Our Consortium

The ShieldBot team is formed by 11 research and industrial partners
from six European countries, coordinated by IDEKO

ShieldBot is a member
of the
**#Tech4EUConstruction
Cluster**

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